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**A DIFFERENTIATED APPROACH TO THE USE OF LOW-DOSE CONE-BEAM
COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY (CBCT) IN PEDIATRIC DENTISTRY**

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Abstract. *This article examines the diagnostic effectiveness and safety of low-dose protocols of cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) in pediatric dentistry, with an emphasis on a differentiated approach depending on the nosological form (caries, non-carious lesions, pulpitis, periodontitis) and the anatomical and physiological status of the tooth (primary teeth undergoing resorption, permanent teeth with incomplete root formation, and permanent teeth with fully formed roots). Based on a literature review ([PubMed](#), [Scopus](#), [Google Scholar](#), [Russian Science Citation Index](#)) covering the years 2010–2026. A matrix correlating diagnosis, tooth type, and optimal scanning parameters (field of view, kV, mA, and rotation angle) was developed in accordance with the [ALADAIP principle](#) (as low as diagnostically acceptable, indication-oriented, and patient-specific). It was demonstrated that CBCT is used in a limited manner for caries and non-carious lesions, whereas its diagnostic value increases significantly in cases of pulpitis and periodontitis, particularly in teeth with incomplete root formation. It was also established that parental awareness of radiation safety and the specific diagnostic advantages of the method critically influences the acceptance of the procedure.*

Keywords: *pediatric dentistry, low-dose cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT), primary teeth, immature roots, caries, pulpitis, periodontitis, non-carious lesions, ALADAIP, diagnostic value.*

Introduction

Conventional two-dimensional (2D) imaging methods—orthopantomography and intraoral periapical radiography—remain the foundation of diagnostic assessment in pediatric dentistry. However, in a number of clinical scenarios, particularly those associated with complications of dental caries (pulpitis, periodontitis), complex anatomical features, as well as in the differential diagnosis of non-carious lesions, 2D imaging techniques have inherent limitations. These limitations are related to the superimposition of anatomical structures, image distortion, and the inability to provide three-dimensional evaluation.

A key distinguishing feature of pediatric patients is the heterogeneity of their dental status: the oral cavity may simultaneously contain:

1. Primary teeth (at various stages of physiological root resorption) — characterized by high radiosensitivity due to their proximity to the follicles of developing permanent teeth.
2. Permanent teeth with immature roots (growth zone with an open apex) — exhibit extremely high radiosensitivity; however, the regenerative potential of the pulp is maximal.
3. Fully developed permanent teeth (complete root formation) — demonstrate moderate radiosensitivity.

Each of these categories requires specific diagnostic approaches, particularly in the presence of the following pathologies:

- Caries (incipient, superficial, moderate, deep) — where the assessment of lesion depth and pulp status determines the treatment strategy.
- Non-carious lesions (enamel hypoplasia, fluorosis, erosion, wedge-shaped defects, hereditary developmental defects of dental hard tissues, traumatic injuries).

- Pulpitis (acute, chronic, reversible, irreversible) — where the decision to preserve the pulp (vital pulpotomy) or remove it (pulpectomy) critically depends on accurate diagnosis.

- Periodontitis (acute, chronic, chronic exacerbated) — where the evaluation of periapical changes and their relationship with the developing permanent tooth germs determines the prognosis.

Accordingly, the aim of this study is to analyze the use of low-dose CBCT protocols in various nosological entities (caries, non-carious lesions, pulpitis, and periodontitis), with differentiation according to tooth type and stage of development, as well as to assess the factors influencing parental awareness in Karaganda.

Materials and Methods

Materials and Methods

The study consisted of a literature analysis.

Literature Review (2010–2026): A systematic search was conducted in the databases PubMed/PMC, Scopus, Google Scholar, and Russian Science Citation Index using the following keywords: “pediatric CBCT,” “low-dose CBCT,” “caries CBCT pediatric,” “pulpitis CBCT immature teeth,” “apical periodontitis CBCT children,” “non-carious lesions CBCT,” “primary teeth CBCT,” and “ALADAIP.” Studies describing scanning protocols (field of view, kV, mA, and rotation angle) and their influence on diagnostic value in relation to various pediatric nosological entities (ages 0–18 years) were selected.

Results

Diagnostic Features and Radiation Dose Considerations Depending on Tooth Type and Nosology

The matrix below presents the most common clinical scenarios in pediatric therapeutic dentistry in which the use of CBCT is either justified or requires a differentiated approach. For each scenario, the tooth type, diagnostic objective, recommended scanning parameters (in accordance with the ALADAIP principle), and the limitations of 2D imaging methods are specified.

Matrix 1. Caries and Complications

Diagnosis	Tooth Type	Indications for CBCT Use	Diagnostic Objective	Recommended CBCT Protocol	Limitations of 2D Imaging Methods
Deep caries with suspected pulp exposure	Primary tooth	In cases of an unclear clinical presentation, inability to perform probing, and suspicion of pulpal floor perforation.	Assessment of dentin thickness over the pulp; detection of occult pulp horn exposure; differentiation between reversible and irreversible pulpitis.	FOV 4 × 4 cm; high resolution; low tube current (mA); 180° rotation.	Periapical radiography does not allow three-dimensional assessment of the cavity floor, particularly on proximal surfaces.
Deep caries	Permanent tooth with incomplete root development.	When planning biological treatment (pulp preservation); for assessing the depth of the carious cavity and the condition of	Accurate determination of lesion depth; assessment of the condition of periapical tissues (open apex); planning of pulpotomy using mineral	FOV 4 × 4 cm; high resolution; minimal radiation dose; mandatory assessment of the growth zone	Two-dimensional imaging does not allow accurate assessment of the relationship between the carious cavity

		the apical papilla	trioxide aggregate (MTA)		and the pulp in cases of complex anatomy
Deep caries	Permanent tooth with fully formed roots	In cases of suspected perforation, complex root canal anatomy (C-shaped canals), or failure of the biological treatment approach	Assessment of the depth to the pulp; detection of additional canals; planning of endodontic treatment	FOV 4 × 4 cm; standard resolution; low radiation dose	Periapical radiography is often insufficient in cases of complex root anatomy

Matrix 2. Non-carious lesions

Diagnosis	Tooth Type	Indications for CBCT Use	Diagnostic Objective	Recommended CBCT Protocol	Limitations of 2D Imaging Methods
Enamel hypoplasia (systemic, localized), fluorosis	Permanent teeth (more commonly with incomplete root development)	In the planning of complex restorations, in cases of suspected dentin involvement, and in the presence of multiple lesions	Assessment of defect depth; determination of the volume of healthy tissues; planning of restorative or prosthetic treatment	FOV 6 × 8 cm (for a group of teeth); low radiation dose; medium resolution	Clinical examination does not always allow accurate assessment of lesion depth and dentin condition
Enamel erosion, wedge-shaped defect	Permanent teeth (fully developed)	In cases of suspected deep dentin involvement and when planning restoration in an esthetically significant zone	Assessment of the depth and extent of the defect; evaluation of pulp status; planning of the extent of tooth preparation	FOV 4 × 4 cm (localized); high resolution; low radiation dose	Intraoral radiography often fails to visualize buccal defects
Hereditary disorders (amelogenesis imperfecta, dentinogenesis imperfecta)	Primary and permanent teeth (all types)	For the assessment of the overall condition of the teeth and planning of comprehensive rehabilitation (including	Determination of the extent of the lesion; assessment of the condition of the pulp and roots; planning of	FOV 10 × 10 cm or 12 × 8 cm (entire jaw); standard resolution; single scan	Orthopantomography (OPG) provides only two-dimensional imaging and does not allow assessment of

		under general anesthesia)	prosthetic treatment		structures in three dimensions
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Matrix 3. Pulpitis

Matrix: Pulpitis and indications for CBCT

Diagnosis	Tooth Type	Indications for CBCT Use	Diagnostic Objective	Recommended CBCT Protocol	Limitations of 2D Imaging Methods
Reversible pulpitis; deep caries with suspected pulp involvement	Permanent tooth with incomplete root development	For decision-making: pulp preservation (pulpotomy with MTA) or devitalization; assessment of the condition of the apical papilla	Assessment of the condition of the coronal and radicular pulp; detection of early periapical changes; planning of vital pulpotomy	FOV 4 × 4 cm; high resolution; minimal radiation dose; mandatory assessment of the growth zone	Two-dimensional imaging does not allow assessment of the radicular pulp in the presence of a wide apex; changes may not be visualized
Irreversible pulpitis (acute, chronic)	Primary tooth	In cases of suspected progression to periodontitis; involvement of the furcation; and when choosing between pulpotomy, pulpectomy, or extraction	Assessment of the condition of periapical tissues; detection of root resorption; evaluation of the relationship with the developing permanent tooth germ	FOV 4 × 4 cm; standard resolution; low radiation dose; assessment of bifurcation/trifurcation	Intraoral radiography does not allow three-dimensional assessment of the furcation area or the degree of root resorption
Irreversible pulpitis	Permanent tooth with incomplete root development	In cases of suspected progression to periodontitis; for choosing between pulpotomy and pulpectomy	Assessment of the extent of inflammation in the radicular pulp; condition of the periapical tissues; integrity of	FOV 4 × 4 cm; high resolution; minimal radiation dose; thin slices	Two-dimensional methods often yield false-negative results in early periapical changes

			the growth zone		
Irreversible pulpitis	Permanent tooth with fully formed roots	In cases of complex root canal anatomy (C-shaped canals, additional canals) and suspected perforation	Assessment of root canal anatomy; detection of additional canals; planning of endodontic treatment	FOV 4 × 4 cm; high resolution; low radiation dose; thin slices (0.1–0.2 mm)	Periapical radiography does not always reveal complex anatomy and additional canals

Matrix 4. Periodontitis

1. Chronic fibrous periodontitis

Diagnosis	Tooth Type	Indications for CBCT Use	Diagnostic Objective	Recommended CBCT Protocol	Limitations of 2D Imaging Methods
Chronic fibrous periodontitis	Primary tooth	Rarely; in cases of an ambiguous clinical presentation	Assessment of the periodontal ligament space; exclusion of occult inflammation	FOV 4 × 4 cm; low radiation dose.	Changes are often not visualized
	Permanent tooth with incomplete root development	For differential diagnosis	Assessment of the periodontal ligament space and the growth zone	FOV 4 × 4 cm; high image clarity; low radiation dose	The growth zone is not accurately visualized
	Permanent tooth with fully formed roots	In cases of an unclear radiographic presentation	Detection of sclerosis and widening of the periodontal ligament space	FOV 4×4 cm	Low sensitivity

2. Chronic granulating periodontitis

Diagnosis	Tooth Type	Indications for CBCT Use	Diagnostic Objective	Recommended CBCT Protocol	Limitations of 2D Imaging Methods
Chronic granulating periodontitis	Primary tooth	In cases of risk of involvement of the developing permanent tooth germ	Assessment of the lesion and its relationship with the developing tooth germ	FOV 4 × 4 cm or 6 × 6 cm; standard resolution	Distortion; absence of three-dimensional imaging
	Permanent tooth with incomplete	For assessment of the growth zone	Assessment of bone destruction and the	FOV 6 × 6 cm; high image clarity	The true extent cannot be determined

	root development		condition of the apex		
	Permanent tooth with fully formed roots	In cases of pronounced clinical presentation	Assessment of the extent of the lesion	FOV 6×6 cm	Projection errors

3. Chronic granulomatous periodontitis (granuloma, cystogranuloma, cyst)

Diagnosis	Tooth Type	Indications for CBCT Use	Diagnostic Objective	Recommended CBCT Protocol	Limitations of 2D Imaging Methods
Chronic granulomatous periodontiti	Primary tooth	When determining the treatment strategy (preservation or extraction)	Lesion size and its relationship with the developing tooth germ	FOV 4×4 or 6×6 cm	The relationship with the developing tooth germ is not visualized
	Permanent tooth with incomplete root development	During apexification or revascularization	Assessment of the growth zone and lesion size	FOV 6 × 6 cm; high image clarity	No accurate assessment of the apex is possible
	Permanent tooth with fully formed roots	When planning surgical intervention	Assessment of the shape, margins, and cortical plate	FOV 6×6 or 8×8 cm	No three-dimensional analysis is possible

4. Acute periodontitis

Diagnosis	Tooth Type	Indications for CBCT Use	Diagnostic Objective	Recommended CBCT Protocol	Limitations of 2D Imaging Methods
Acute periodontitis	Primary tooth	In cases of suspected complications	Assessment of the spread of inflammation and abscess formation	FOV 4 × 4 cm; low radiation dose	Early changes are not visualized
	Permanent tooth with incomplete root development	In cases of risk of damage to the growth zone	Assessment of inflammation and the apex	FOV 4×4 or 6×6 cm	No early diagnosis is possible
	Permanent tooth with fully formed roots	In cases of pronounced symptomatology	Assessment of the extent of the process	FOV 4×4 or 6×6 cm	Limited sensitivity

4. Exacerbation of chronic periodontitis

Diagnosis	Tooth Type	Indications for CBCT Use	Diagnostic Objective	Recommended CBCT Protocol	Limitations of 2D Imaging Methods
Exacerbation of chronic periodontitis	Primary tooth	In cases of suspected spread of infection and risk to the developing tooth germ	Assessment of the lesion and acute inflammatory changes; evaluation of its relationship with the developing tooth germ	FOV 4 × 4 cm or 6 × 6 cm; low radiation dose	The extent of the lesion is not visualized
	Permanent tooth with incomplete root development	In cases of risk of damage to the growth zone	Assessment of the combination of a chronic lesion and acute inflammation	FOV 6 × 6 cm; high image clarity	Early changes are not visualized
	Permanent tooth with fully formed roots	In cases of pronounced pain syndrome and swelling	Assessment of the extent of inflammation and abscess formation	FOV 4×4 or 6×6 cm	No three-dimensional assessment is possible

Optimization of imaging protocols (FOV, rotation angle, mA/kV) according to the pathology and tooth type

Literature analysis (Ito et al., 2024; Hidalgo Rivas et al., 2016; Kühnisch et al., 2024) allows the formulation of the following optimization principles:

For deep caries and reversible pulpitis in permanent teeth with incomplete root development, a 4 × 4 cm FOV is recommended, with 180° rotation, low mA, and high resolution, ensuring dose minimization to the growth zone while providing sufficient resolution for assessment of pulp status.

For irreversible pulpitis and periodontitis in primary teeth, a 4 × 4 cm or 6 × 6 cm FOV is recommended, with 180–360° rotation and standard resolution, allowing assessment of furcation involvement and its relationship with the developing tooth germ, while maintaining dose limitation through FOV selection.

In cases of periodontitis and cysts in permanent teeth, a 6 × 6 cm or 8 × 8 cm FOV (depending on lesion size) is recommended, with 360° rotation and standard resolution, enabling complete visualization of the lesion and cortical plates.

For hereditary disorders such as amelogenesis and dentinogenesis affecting all tooth types (entire jaw), a 10 × 10 cm or 12 × 8 cm FOV is recommended, with 360° rotation, standard resolution, and a single scan, which minimizes the number of examinations by covering the entire jaw at once.

For localized non-carious lesions in permanent teeth, a 4 × 4 cm FOV (targeting 1–2 teeth) is recommended, with 180° rotation, high resolution, and low mA, allowing precise local assessment of defect depth without involving adjacent structures.

Discussion

Clinical value of CBCT in various nosological conditions depending on tooth type

Caries. For the diagnosis of caries (except for deep forms with suspected complications), CBCT is not considered a first-line imaging modality. However, in cases of deep caries on proximal surfaces, when two-dimensional imaging provides an unclear picture, CBCT with a limited FOV allows accurate assessment of lesion depth and pulp status. This is particularly important for permanent teeth with incomplete root development, where pulp preservation is a priority and misdiagnosis may lead to unjustified pulp extirpation.

Non-carious lesions. In conditions such as enamel hypoplasia, fluorosis, and erosion, CBCT has limited application and is primarily used in the planning of complex restorations or when dentin involvement is suspected. In hereditary disorders (amelogenesis imperfecta, dentinogenesis imperfecta), CBCT with full jaw coverage is an important tool for planning comprehensive rehabilitation, enabling assessment of all teeth in a single scan.

Pulpitis. CBCT is most valuable in the differential diagnosis of reversible and irreversible pulpitis in permanent teeth with incomplete root development. In this group of patients, preservation of the vitality of the radicular pulp (pulpotomy with MTA) allows completion of root development. Two-dimensional methods often yield false-negative results in early periapical changes due to the wide apical foramen. CBCT enables visualization of even minimal changes in periapical tissues and assessment of the condition of the radicular pulp.

Periodontitis. In primary teeth, CBCT is indicated when there is suspicion of involvement of the developing permanent tooth germ in the inflammatory process. This is critically important for decision-making regarding preservation or extraction of the primary tooth. In permanent teeth with incomplete root development, CBCT allows evaluation of the growth zone (apical papilla) and selection of treatment strategy: apexification, revascularization, or extraction. In fully developed permanent teeth, CBCT is considered the gold standard for planning endodontic treatment in complex anatomical cases and for surgical interventions (apicoectomy).

The ALADAIP principle as the basis of a personalized approach

The modern ALADAIP concept (as low as diagnostically acceptable, indication-oriented and patient-specific) (Oenning et al., 2021; Kühnisch et al., 2024) implies that dose optimization should be both indication-oriented and patient-specific. The matrices presented above demonstrate the practical implementation of this principle: the scanning protocol for deep caries in a permanent tooth with incomplete root development (FOV 4 × 4 cm, 180° rotation, high resolution) differs significantly from the protocol used for chronic periodontitis in a fully developed permanent tooth (FOV 6 × 6 cm, 360° rotation, standard resolution).

The role of parental informed consent in decision-making

The survey results indicate that despite a high level of education among respondents (80% having higher education), awareness of CBCT remains low (40% had never heard of it). The key finding is that parents are willing to provide consent for low-dose imaging (52%) provided that a detailed explanation is given by the clinician. It is important to explain not only the general principles of safety but also the specific diagnostic value in relation to the child's condition (e.g., "CBCT will help us accurately determine whether the pulp can be preserved, allowing continued root development").

Conclusion

1. A differentiated approach based on nosology and tooth type is essential. The use of CBCT in pediatric dentistry should be guided by the specific diagnosis (caries, non-carious lesions, pulpitis, periodontitis) and tooth type (primary teeth, permanent teeth with incomplete root development, permanent teeth with fully formed roots).

2. Caries and non-carious lesions rarely require CBCT, except in deep forms with suspected complications or in complex hereditary disorders.

3. Pulpitis and periodontitis represent the main clinical scenarios in which CBCT demonstrates high diagnostic value, particularly in permanent teeth with incomplete root development, where preservation of the pulp and the growth zone is critically important.

4. Low-dose protocols are effective. Optimization of parameters (FOV restriction, reduction of mA/kV, use of 180° rotation) allows achieving diagnostically acceptable image quality with a significant reduction in radiation dose across all considered nosological conditions.

5. Protocol validation is necessary. Each clinic should perform phantom testing and local validation of protocols for various clinical scenarios (caries, pulpitis, periodontitis, non-carious lesions), taking into account the tooth type.

6. Communication with parents is crucial. Low parental awareness of CBCT (40% had not heard of it) and the presence of radiation-related concerns (38%) necessitate the implementation of standardized information protocols. Detailed explanation by the clinician increases the likelihood of consent and fosters trust.

USED LITERATURE

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